

Editorial Acknowledgment

This issue features seven articles that were presented at the [17th International Conference on Educational Data Mining \(EDM 2024\)](#), these articles are extended versions of papers presented at EDM 2024 that took place in Atlanta, USA, July 14-17, 2024. This issue features as well one regular article and three articles selected by the Journal track editors for the [18th International Conference on Educational Data Mining \(EDM 2025\)](#); these articles are full length JEDM articles that are also presented at the conference that will take place in Palermo, Italy July 20-23, 2025.

For the eleventh time, EDM 2025 will hold a Journal track allowing papers accepted to JEDM to be presented at the conference. The JEDM Track at EDM 2025 received 15 submissions, among which three made it to the final stage in time for publication in this issue. A fourth work will be published in the next issue. We are pleased to accept and publish the following works JEDM track:

Wen Chiang Lim, Neil T. Heffernan, and Adam Sales examine the impact of teachers' viewing and use of assignment reports on student outcomes, utilizing data from ASSISTments, an online platform providing teachers with content and problems on mathematics. Their paper, titled *Evaluating the Effects of Assignment Report Usage on Student Outcomes in an Intelligent Tutoring System: A Randomized-Encouragement Design*, provides robust evidence that teachers' viewing of the first assignment positively influences student completion of the second assignment.

The paper *Predicting Perceived Text Complexity: The Role of Person-Related Features in Profile-Based Models* by **Boris Thome, Friederike Hertweck, and Stefan Conrad** compares multiple machine learning models as well as LLMs for the purpose of predicting text complexity as perceived by students from various backgrounds. The results indicate that K-Nearest Neighbors and Multilayer Perceptron perform well in predicting perceived text complexity, while the LLMs analyzed in the research did not surpass baseline models.

The paper *Using a Randomized Experiment to Compare Mastery Learning Thresholds* by **Jeffrey Matayoshi, Eric Cosyn, Hasan Uzun, and Eyad Kurd-Misto** investigates the relationship between different mastery learning thresholds of the ALEKS intelligent tutoring system and the long-term retention of the learned knowledge. The results indicate that, although the high mastery threshold requires more practice and time from students, the differences in knowledge retention are relatively small and decrease over time.

A final paper will appear in our next issue, *Developing Feedback Taxonomy for Math: A Synergy of Perspectives through Data Mining Methods* **Seiyon Lee, Sami Baral, Hongming (Chip) Li, Li Cheng, Shan Zhang, Carly Siegel Thorp, Jennifer St. John, Tamisha Thompson, Neil T. Heffernan, and Anthony F. Botelho** use data mining methods to extract key feedback types for open-ended mathematics questions. The work results in the development of a taxonomy that has the potential to support more consistent feedback processes across learning platforms.

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The Editor and Associate Editors would like to warmly thank the editorial board and colleagues who kindly served as special reviewers in 2024. Their professionalism and support are much appreciated.

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